

STUDIES ON TOXICITY OF DIMETHYL SULPHOXIDE ON THE INDIAN MAJOR CARP, *LABEO ROHITA*

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ABSTRACT

DMSO is frequently used as carrier solvent in toxicological experiments due to its exceptionally low toxicity and environmental impact and also to achieve more effective dispersion of the toxicants. Aquatic toxicity studies of DMSO on the respiratory rates and the biochemical constituents of muscle and liver in *Labeo rohita* revealed the minimal lethality and negligible effect on the physiology of the test organism. This study helps in the choice of percentage of the carrier solvent that can be used in the preparation of toxicants for any toxicological studies involving fish.

Keywords: Aquatic toxicity, Dimethyl sulphoxide, Respiratory rates, Biochemical constituents, *Labeo rohita*.

INTRODUCTION

Any variation in the environment acts as a stress on the organisms. When a pesticide or any pollutant reaches the aquatic ecosystem, the fish are exposed to severe stress and as a natural instinct; the fish tend to adapt themselves by reacting suitably to overcome the stress. Freshwater ecosystem consists of a large number of fauna and flora in them. These aquatic organisms are very sensitive to even a slight alteration in the environment. In an aquatic environment the pollutants reach easily as runoff from pesticide residues and heavy metals like copper, mercury, nickel, lead and zinc pollute the aquatic system through industrial and municipal wastes (Presley and Long bottom, 1982). As fishes are the major inhabitants of aquatic life, hazards to the fish population are a matter of great concern for fishery industry.

Pesticides are used in agricultural practice to cope up with the problems created by the insect pests, which result in crop loss. The impact of pesticide on environment is grave. Pesticides enter water bodies through urban and industrial wastewater discharge, surface run-off from non-point sources. Pesticides are relatively persistent and accumulate at high rates in aquatic organisms.

Toxicity of a substance is known by its capacity to cause adverse effects on the living organisms. Subsequently, the toxic substances are absorbed into the viscera by various routes causing an internal exposure

(Tilak *et al.*, 2005). Within the body of an organism, the substances are converted into metabolites which may either be more toxic or less toxic.

Toxic impact may bring about physiological, biochemical or pathological alterations in the organisms; the signs of toxicity may reveal symptoms of illness varying from simple local effects-structural and behavioral (Shivakumar *et al.*, 2005) to complex disorders resulting in mortality. The sequence of events and interaction of toxic substances with target molecules of organism depend on various factors such as the nature of the toxicant, duration of exposure, physiological state of the organism, biotic and abiotic factors of environment (Subramanian, 2004).

Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) is the organosulfur compound with the formula (CH₃)₂SO. This colorless liquid is an important polaraprotic solvent that dissolves both polar and nonpolar compounds and is miscible in a wide range of organic solvents as well as water. It has a distinctive property of penetrating the skin very readily, so that one may taste it soon after it comes into contact with the skin. Dimethyl sulfoxide is produced from dimethyl sulfide, a by-product of kraft pulping. It is industrially produced by oxidation of dimethyl sulfide with oxygen or nitrogen dioxide. DMSO is frequently used as a solvent for chemical reactions involving salts, most notably Finkelstein reactions and other nucleophilic substitutions. It is also extensively used as an extractant in biochemistry

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and cell biology. Because DMSO is only weakly acidic, it tolerates relatively strong bases and as such has been extensively used in the study of carbanions.

Because of its high boiling point, 189 °C (372 °F), DMSO evaporates slowly at normal atmospheric pressure. Samples dissolved in DMSO cannot be as easily recovered compared to other solvents, as it is very difficult to remove all traces of DMSO by conventional rotary evaporation, one technique to fully recover samples is removal of the organic solvent by evaporation followed by addition of water (to dissolve DMSO) and lyophilisation to remove both DMSO and water.

DMSO is an important solvent for small molecule studies as it provides a nearly universal approach for the solubilisation of small molecules. Because of its physicochemical properties, high solvent power, low chemical reactivity and relatively low toxicity, DMSO has become the solvent of choice (Johannesson *et al.*, 1997) for such studies. DMSO is the most common solvent carrier used in aquatic toxicity tests to prepare miscible concentrations of the chemical toxicants in order to help achieve more effective dispersion of the toxicants (Hutchinson *et al.*, 2006).

In aquatic toxicological studies involving biological organisms, the effect of the principal toxicant is the most crucial aspect. Some of the toxicants require an additive or a carrier solvent to make it miscible in the medium due to poor water solubility of chemicals and this could result in an independent effect of stress on the organism by such solvents. In this scenario, the study helps in assessing the effects of such solvents exerted on the test organism.

The present study is an attempt to investigate the effect of the DMSO on the respiratory rates and the biochemical components (Total sugars, Total proteins and Total lipids) of muscle and liver tissues of one of the commercially important and widely cultured Indian Major Carps, *Labeo rohita*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Rohita fingerlings of the same size (5.5 – 6.0 cm in length and 7.5– 8.0 g in weight) were procured from private culture ponds and brought to the laboratory in oxygen packs. The fish were acclimatized and maintained in ferrocement tanks (3'L x 2'W x 2'H) filled with bore well water. The stock fish were fed with pelleted feed prepared with tapioca powder, groundnut oil cake, rice bran and mineral mixture (Omprakasam and Manohar, 1991) at 5% body weight in two split doses. Feeding was stopped 24 hr prior to experimentation.

Apparently healthy fish were selected for experiments and maintained in disinfected glass aquarium tanks (2'L x 1'W x 1'H) filled with water at the rate of 2 litres per fish. Four experimental groups were maintained with aqueous solutions of DMSO (EMerck-AR grade) at the rate of 0.5%, 1.0%, 1.5 % and 2.0% (v/v), along with suitable controls without the toxicant.

Observations were made for structural behavioral and internal pathological conditions. Ten fish from control as well as experimental groups were sacrificed for the study of selected parameters on Day Zero, 4th day and 7th day of experimentation. Standard protocols were followed for the analyses.

Rate of oxygen consumption was estimated by titrimetric method following modified Winkler's method (Anon, 1984)

For the analyses of biochemical parameters, muscle and liver tissues were dissected out from the control and experimental fish after the analysis of respiratory rate.

Colorimetric method was followed for the biochemical analyses using Spectronic-21 (Bausche and Lomb) spectrophotometer. Total sugars was estimated by anthrone method (Carrol *et al.*, 1956) and the total protein content in the tissues was done by folin phenol method (Lowry *et al.*, 1951), while for the estimation of total lipids, the method of Bligh and Dyer (Jayaraman, 1988) was followed.

The results were tabulated with means of ten values and expressed as Mean \pm SEM for all the conditions and parameters. Students't' test was applied to assess the statistical significance between two means.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Rohita fingerlings exposed to DMSO were found to be lethargic and did not respond to stimuli. Swimming activity was incoherent with occasional darting and whirling movement. Frequent surfacing and gasping were also prominently observed. These symptoms of abnormal behavior were clearly evident only for a few hours after exposure to the toxicant and regained normalcy within 24 hrs, indicating the initial adaptive response of the test fish to stress imposed by the toxicant. This shows that the toxicant DMSO is least toxic in nature and unable to evoke any lethal effect as observed by Willford (1988) in trouts and bluegills. This is confirmed by the fact that there is no mortality among the test population in any of the concentrations. The internal visceral organization of the fish also did not reveal any symptoms of poisoning or degeneration up to 7th day of exposure even at higher concentration of 2% DMSO. In the absence of any direct evidences of effects of DMSO in fish, the conditions obtained in the present investigation are inferred based on the effects of other toxicants on the aquatic organisms.

The respiratory rate of the fish was steadily on the rise from zero day to 4th to 7th day in both the control as well as all the experimental group of fish under stress induced by DMSO (Table 1). In the treated fish, the rate of oxygen consumption was more compared to the increase noted in the untreated fish. This can be corroborated with the hyperactivity of the fish to overcome the induced stress. In aquatic organisms, the respiratory rate is an indicator of physiologic state (Yang *et al.*, 2000; Santhakumar and Balaji, 2000; Bhattacharya, 2001; Nanda *et al.*, 2002). Biochemical parameters of the tissues reflect the metabolic state of the fish and are influenced by pollutants and

toxicants leading to death due to impaired and uncompensatory metabolic profiles.

Though there appears no documentation of the effects of DMSO, the biochemical constituents of the tissues of fishes have been shown to vary under the influence of heavy metals (Dhanapakiam and Ramasamy, 2001; Meha *et al.*, 2004). Similarly the pesticides also cause severe alterations in the tissue biochemistry of fishes as evinced by (Kumar and Singh, 2000; Tilak *et al.*, 2003; Mathivanan, 2004; Shrivastava and Singh, 2004).

In the present study, the fingerlings of rohita showed changes in the total sugars (Table 2 & 3), total proteins (Table 4 & 5) and total lipids (Table 6 & 7) under the influence of different concentrations of DMSO on the different days of exposure. Total sugar content in the muscle and liver tissues of fish exposed to DMSO was reduced compared to their respective controls. Liver being the site of metabolism, the carbohydrates tend to accumulate for metabolic processes to occur. The fish not exposed to toxicant showed a normal trend with 26.25 mg/g on zero day, 32.55 mg/g on 4th day and reduced to 25.88 mg/g on 7th day. This reduction may be attributed to utilization of carbohydrate source available, with replenishment of sources not possible due to starvation.

Protein remains more in the muscle tissues than in the liver because of the requirement of growth factors and energy regulation needed for the swimming activity. The total protein content was depleted from 85.38 mg/g on zero day to 46.82 mg/g on 4th day control group and remained at 59.23 mg/g on 7th day. This suggests that utilization of the protein content. Compared to this, in the fish under stress due to the exposure to DMSO, the protein content was very much reduced in both the muscle and liver tissues. This suggests that the gluconeogenetic pathway has been initiated to supplement depletion of sugars by

breaking down of protein to yield sugars. This becomes evident when seen together with the trend observed in the total sugar content of the tissues.

The lipids remain accumulated as reserve metabolic source to compensate for excessive loss of sugars and proteins due to impairment of physiological processes, particularly under stress. The observations made in the total lipid content of the muscle and liver tissues of the control and experimental group of fishes were in conformity to normal metabolic profiles. There is a steady accumulation of lipid from zero day to 7th day, suggesting non conversion of excess lipid to sugars by gluconeogenetic path way. This may be due to the fact that the fish were exposed to short term toxicity for 7 days only in the present study. If the study is extended for a longer duration, the lipid content also would have been utilized to compensate for the hypoglycemia and hypoproteinemia caused by the toxicant-induced stress.

The observations in this study confirm the least toxic nature of DMSO (up to 2.0% concentration) to cause any observable changes in the metabolic profile or to induce any pathological condition as an independent toxicant in the fingerlings of rohita. This suggests that DMSO can be a safe solvent to carry out any toxicological studies. Moreover, majority of the chemical compounds require DMSO at 1.0% concentration in the medium to dissolve and remain stable for various studies and there appears no pathological changes in the test organism at this concentration as revealed by the present investigation.

In biological organisms, the toxic effects of the pollutants or toxicants vary depending on other biotic and abiotic factors like environmental parameters, age, dose and duration of exposure to the toxicants. Moreover, the toxic effect will be more when two or more toxicants act together in a synergistic manner (Sujatha, 2006).

Table 1. Effect of Dimethyl sulphoxide on oxygen consumption (ml/g/hr) of *Labeo rohita*.

Concentration	Zero Day	4 th day Control	4 th day Treated	7 th Day control	7 th day Treated
0.5%	0.07 ± 0.02	0.198 ± 0.010	0.353 ± 0.02	0.22 ± 0.02	0.494 ± 0.02
1.0%	0.07 ± 0.02	0.198 ± 0.010	0.392 ± 0.01	0.22 ± 0.02	0.484 ± 0.01
1.5%	0.07 ± 0.02	0.198 ± 0.010	0.213 ± 0.010	0.22 ± 0.02	0.374 ± 0.01
2.0%	0.07 ± 0.02	0.198 ± 0.010	0.271 ± 0.01	0.22 ± 0.02	0.293 ± 0.01

Table 2. Effect of Dimethyl sulphoxide in the muscle total sugar (mg/g wet wt) of *Labeo rohita*.

Concentration	Zero Day	4 th day Control	4 th day Treated	7 th Day control	7 th day Treated
0.5%	0.97 ± 0.03	1.89 ± 0.02	3.42 ± 0.05	2.75 ± 0.05	1.841 ± 0.14
1.0%	0.97 ± 0.03	1.89 ± 0.02	2.97 ± 0.02	2.75 ± 0.05	2.052 ± 0.15
1.5%	0.97 ± 0.03	1.89 ± 0.02	3.56 ± 0.32	2.75 ± 0.05	2.843 ± 0.07
2.0%	0.97 ± 0.03	1.89 ± 0.02	5.92 ± 0.17	2.75 ± 0.05	2.052 ± 0.07

Table 3. Effect of Dimethyl sulphoxide in the liver total sugar (mg/g wet wt) of *Labeo rohita*.

Concentration	Zero Day	4 th day Control	4 th day Treated	7 th Day control	7 th day Treated
0.5%	26.25 ± 0.35	32.55 ± 0.79	13.56 ± 0.57	25.88 ± 2.56	23.02 ± 0.21
1.0%	26.25 ± 0.35	32.55 ± 0.79	14.40 ± 0.13	25.88 ± 2.56	24.18 ± 0.12
1.5%	26.25 ± 0.35	32.55 ± 0.79	24.56 ± 0.86	25.88 ± 2.56	28.14 ± 0.94
2.0%	26.25 ± 0.35	32.55 ± 0.79	18.11 ± 0.21	25.88 ± 2.56	24.82 ± 0.14

Table 4. Effect of Dimethyl sulphoxide in the muscle total proteins (mg/g wet wt) of *Labeo rohita*.

Concentration	Zero Day	4 th day Control	4 th day Treated	7 th Day control	7 th day Treated
0.5%	85.38 ± 0.24	46.82 ± 0.79	36.88 ± 0.70	59.23 ± 1.39	50.19 ± 1.74
1.0%	85.38 ± 0.24	46.82 ± 0.79	45.32 ± 1.23	59.23 ± 1.39	52.70 ± 1.26
1.5%	85.38 ± 0.24	46.82 ± 0.79	32.55 ± 1.42	59.23 ± 1.39	51.25 ± 1.65
2.0%	85.38 ± 0.24	46.82 ± 0.79	33.01 ± 1.81	59.23 ± 1.39	49.70 ± 0.79

Table 5. Effect of Dimethyl sulphoxide in the liver total proteins (mg/g wet wt) of *Labeo rohita*.

Concentration	Zero Day	4 th day Control	4 th day Treated	7 th Day control	7 th day Treated
0.5%	52.31 ± 2.14	38.30 ± 1.33	25.50 ± 0.32	44.87 ± 2.14	24.78 ± 0.45
1.0%	52.31 ± 2.14	38.30 ± 1.33	22.15 ± 1.15	44.87 ± 2.14	29.35 ± 0.94
1.5%	52.31 ± 2.14	38.30 ± 1.33	21.45 ± 8.90	44.87 ± 2.14	25.02 ± 1.02
2.0%	52.31 ± 2.14	38.30 ± 1.33	20.37 ± 0.46	44.87 ± 2.14	27.99 ± 0.89

Table 6. Effect of Dimethyl sulphoxide in the muscle total lipids (mg/g wet wt) of *Labeo rohita*.

Concentration	Zero Day	4 th day Control	4 th day Treated	7 th Day control	7 th day Treated
0.5%	31.64 ± 0.23	36.22 ± 0.19	146.97 ± 0.17	72.55 ± 0.15	114.99 ± 0.17
1.0%	31.64 ± 0.23	37.22 ± 0.19	158.19 ± 0.22	72.55 ± 0.15	148.16 ± 0.31
1.5%	31.64 ± 0.23	37.22 ± 0.19	127.49 ± 0.23	72.55 ± 0.15	130.41 ± 0.25
2.0%	31.64 ± 0.23	37.22 ± 0.19	100.29 ± 0.28	72.55 ± 0.15	108.40 ± 0.18

Table 7. Effect of Dimethyl sulphoxide in the liver total lipids (mg/g wet wt) of *Labeo rohita*.

Concentration	Zero Day	4 th day Control	4 th day Treated	7 th Day control	7 th day Treated
0.5%	55.38 ± 0.57	123.58 ± 0.15	198.8 ± 0.26	229.62 ± 0.25	245.32 ± 0.29
1.0%	55.38 ± 0.57	123.58 ± 0.15	232.64 ± 0.16	229.62 ± 0.25	217.99 ± 0.24
1.5%	55.38 ± 0.57	123.58 ± 0.15	236.58 ± 0.17	229.62 ± 0.25	287.49 ± 0.23
2.0%	55.38 ± 0.57	123.58 ± 0.15	242.5 ± 0.23	229.62 ± 0.25	252.6 ± 0.22

CONCLUSION

The present study clearly indicates that DMSO is safe to use as carrier solvent in aquatic toxicity studies of chemical compounds, as it is least toxic to induce any observable pathological conditions as an independent toxicant.

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REFERENCES

- Anon, 1984. Water quality management in aquaculture, (CMFRI Special publication No.22). CMFRI, Cochin.
- Bhattacharya, S., 2001. Stress response to pesticides and heavy metals in fish and other vertebrates. *Proc. Indian. Nat. Acad.*, 673, 215-246.

- Carrol, W.V, Longley, R.W. and Roe, J.H., 1956. The determination of glycogen in the liver and muscle by the use of Anthrone reagent. *J. Biol. Chem.*, 220, 583-593.
- Dhanapakiam, P. and Ramasamy, V.K., 2001. Toxic effects of copper and zinc mixtures on some haematological and biochemical parameters in common carp, *Cyprinus carpio* (Linn.). *J. Environ. Biol.*, 22, 105-116.
- Hutchinson, T.H, Shillabeer, N, Winter, M.J. and Pickford, D.B., 2006. Acute and chronic effects of carrier solvents in aquatic organisms: A critical review. *Aquatic Toxicol.*, 76, 69-92.
- Jayaraman, J., 1988. Laboratory Manual in Biochemistry. 1st Edition, Wiley Eastern Ltd, New Delhi, p. 96.
- Johannesson, H, Denisov, V.P. and Halle, B., 1997. Dimethyl sulfoxide binding to globular proteins: A nuclear magnetic relaxation dispersion study. *Protein Sci.*, 6, 1756-1763.
- Kumar, S. and Singh, M., 2000. Toxicity of dimethoate to a freshwater teleost, *Catla catla* (Ham.). *J. Exp. Biol.*, 3, 83-88.
- Lowry, O.H., Rosebrough, N.J., Farr, A.L. and Randall, R.J., 1951. Protein measurement with folin phenol reagent. *J. Biol. Chem.*, 193, 265-275.
- Mathivanan, R. 2004. Effects of sublethal concentration of quinalphos on selected respiratory and biochemical parameters in the freshwater fish, *Oreochromis mossambicus*. *J. Ecotoxicol. Environ. Monit.*, 14, 57-64.
- Meha, B., Vankhede, G.N. and Dhande, R.R., 2004. Heavy metal induced Biochemical alterations in the freshwater fish *Labeo rohita*. *J. Ecotoxicol Environ. Monit.*, 14, 1-7.
- Nanda, P.L., Nath, D.P. and Behera, K.M., 2002. Respiratory metabolism of fish *Oreochromis mossambicus* (Peters) exposed to pulp and paper mill effluents. *Env. Eco.*, 20, 570-572.
- Omprakasam, M. and Manohar, L., 1991. Experimental infection of some bacterial fish pathogens in the cichlid fish, *Oreochromis mossambicus*. *Indian J. Fish.*, 38, 106-110.
- Presley, T.A. and Longbottom, J.E., 1982. The determination of benomyl and carbendazim in Municipal and Industrial Wastewater. *Method*, 631. EPA-600/4-82-012. PB82-156068.
- Santhakumar, M. and Balaji, M., 2000. Acute toxicity of an organophosphorus insecticide monocrotophos and its effects on behaviour of an air breathing fish *Anabas testudineus* (Bloch). *J. Environ. Biol.*, 21, 121-123.
- Shivakumar, R. and Mushigeri, S. and Davie, B.M., 2005. Effect of Endosulfan to freshwater fish *Ctenopharyngodon idellus*. *J. Ecotoxl. Environ. Monit.*, 15, 113-116.
- Shrivastava, S. and Singh, S. 2004. Changes in protein content in the muscle of *Heteropneustes fossilis* exposed to carbaryl. *J. Ecotoxicol. Environ. Monit.*, 14, 119-122.
- Subramanian, M.A., 2004. Toxicology: Principles and Methods. MJP Publishers, Chennai, p. 202.
- Sujatha, L.B., 2006. Studies on the physiology, haematology and histopathology in the Indian major carp, *Catla catla* (Hamilton), as influenced by individual and synergistic toxic effects of a pesticide and two metallic compounds. Ph.D. Thesis, University of Madras.
- Tilak. K.S., Koteswra Rao and Veeraiah, D., 2005. Effects of chlorpyrifos on histopathology of fish *Catla catla*. *J. Ecotoxicol. Environ. Monit.*, 15(2), 127-140.
- Tilak, K.S, Satyavardhan, K. and Thathaji, P.B., 2003. Biochemical changes induced by fenvalerate in the freshwater fish *Channa punctatus*. *J. Ecotoxicol. Environ. Monit.*, 13, 261-270.
- Willford, W.A., 1988. Toxicity of dimethyl sulfoxide to fish, in Investigations in fish control (Resource publication) United States Bureau of Sport Fisheries and Wildlife. No. 37, p.8.
- Yang, R, Brauner, C., Thurston, V., Neuman, J. and Randall, D.J., 2000. Relationship between toxicant transfer kinetic processes and fish oxygen consumption. *Aqua. Toxicol.*, 48, 95-108.